

INSURGENCY AS A STUMBLING BLOCK TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INDUSTRY OF KASHMIR VALLEY

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Abstract: - The current study contributes to show that how the current political disturbance effects the tourism sector of Kashmir valley. The study contains the analysis on tourism sector of Kashmir which became the major casualty during the years of insurgency. The present study contains both secondary and primary sources of data. In primary phase interview schedule has been used as a source for data collection. It was employed with great precision to get the accurate magnitude. The secondary phase contains information from journals, books, research papers and official reports related to insurgency.

Key words: Tourism, Insurgency, Kashmir, Valley, Political disturbances, income, employment.

Introduction: Violence is not a stone in the hand. It grows like a poison tree inside other people who have not learned to value other human beings. In a democratic world the issue between the two political parties is the conflict. Which create the crises & side the people? The ground reality & the gravity of an itty/bitty issue in politics are the results of huge violence & major unrest. In which the peace is a myth for such conditions, where the pacifists are the ragged insane of that time.

Jammu and Kashmir is among the northern states of India which is divided into three divisions namely Jammu, Kashmir and Ladakh. These three divisions got much importance in tourism sector, among these Kashmir valleys got much tourist resorts by which tourism is called the backbone of Kashmir economy. It covers huge area of employment both in rural and in urban economy. The wonderful nature catches a large number of tourists from our nation and also from whole world by which economy of valley generates. But due to continue political disturbances in valley all sectors of Kashmir economy where most horrible knock down, tourism industry is one of the main industries which affect a lot. There are lots of unexplained things which give rise to political unrest and cause violent behavior among the common

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masses. In short on the end of every violence period common people are repeatedly suffered.

Literature review

Tourism plays a vital role in the economic development of a number of countries across the globe. Known for its extravagant and breathtaking beauty throughout the world, Kashmir has aptly been described as “The Paradise on Earth”. Kashmir is second to no place in the world as far as its natural beauty and rich cultural heritage is concerned. Bubbling streams, lush green meadows and lily-laden lakes- the valley of Kashmir is any tourist’s dream (Dar S. A 2015)¹. The variegation in states tourism sector in the form of nature tourism, cultural tourism, adventure tourism, pilgrimage tourism, leisure tourism etc. has attracted tourist of every nature irrespective of space as a result of which, this sector has been the mainstay of state’s economy (Bhat Bilal 2014)². J&K is an important tourist destination of the country and has been a place of attraction for tourists since centuries. The lush green forests, sweet springs, perennial rivers, pictures que, alpines scenery and pleasant climate of Kashmir valley has remained an internationally acclaimed tourist destination, whereas Jammu region- the land of temples is attracting a large number of pilgrim, tourists (Sharma, R 2012)³. During the last two and half decades Jammu and Kashmir has been under the political turmoil. During the turmoil hundreds and thousands of precious lives have been wasted. When we look into the circumstances in Jammu and Kashmir it is not only the precious lives that has been lost, other segments of the state also received a considerable down fall (Ismal A 2014)⁴. Turmoil in the State, particularly of last two decades, hindered the smooth growth of the tourism and had discouraged most of the travelers from visiting India’s most popular tourist destination. Add to this it also affected not only tourism but also indirectly the economic activities related to tourism (Itoo, M.A 2011)². The valley of Kashmir has been engulfed in a violent situation since 1989, which has threatened the

sustainability of tourism industry. The political instability in turn has greatly altered the direction, flow, pattern and volume of tourists to the destination (Shah, S. A 2014)³.

Objectives

- ✓ To study the Impact of insurgency on tourism industry in Kashmir valley
- ✓ To study tourism industry as the back bone of Kashmir valley
- ✓ To observe the present condition of tourism in Kashmir valley

Materials and Methods

This study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data is collected from direct communication with tourists and related persons with tourism industry in valley, and secondary data has been collected from Government of Jammu and Kashmir digest of statistics, books, journals, newspapers, published and unpublished research work, various search engines, are also used.

Results and Discussion

The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines tourism as “*the activities of persons travelling to, and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited*”.

The history of tourism is as old as the human society itself. The early tourism can be traced from the period when man set sail and attempted to know the immediate world around. His inherent zeal for enchanted unknown lands and curiosity for new world culminated into every travels. At the start of the present century, travel and tourism were confined only to affluent few, i.e., rich, religious zealots, conquerors, the well-educated and the elites who were fascinated by the enchanting beauty and mysteries of unknown land. Tourism has, however, grow from the pursuits of a privileged few to a mass movement of people, and with the urge to discover the unknown places and to seek change

in environment and to undergo new experiences⁷.

Kashmir is one of the most beautiful tourist destinations of the world. It used to attract enormous number of domestic and international tourists before 1989. The period between 1989 and 1998 is a lean period from the tourist's point of view. The unstable political conditions of the valley, the slogan of freedom discouraged the tourists to visit the valley. Tourism, however, is a dominant economic activity in the state especially in Kashmir valley. Moreover, about 20% of the workforce of state is directly or indirectly dependent on tourism⁸.

Table 1.1: Tourist Arrivals to Kashmir Valley from 1987 to 2014 (In 0000s)

Year	Total	% Growth rate
1987	721.62	
1988	722.04	0.06
1989	557.97	-22.72
1990	10.72	-98.08
1991	6.29	-41.36
1992	10.32	64.21
1993	8.03	-22.26
1994	9.81	22.28
1995	8.52	-13.19
1996	9.97	16.98
1997	16.14	61.91
1998	109.88	580.90
1999	217.29	97.75
2000	111.91	-48.50
2001	72.59	-35.14
2002	27.36	-62.31
2003	191.16	598.80
2004	376.73	97.07
2005	605.38	60.69
2006	432.89	-28.49

2007	441.84	2.07
2008	572.63	29.60
2009	601.25	5.00
2010	614.06	2.13
2011	1315.48	114.23
2012	1308.05	-0.56
2013	1172.01	-10.40
2014	1167.62	-0.37

Source: Directorate of Tourism Govt. of Jammu and Kashmir

Finger 1.1: Percentage Growth rate of tourists

Source: Directorate of Tourism Govt. of Jammu and Kashmir

In the above table 1.1 it has been clearly understandable that there is a huge impact of insurgency on the tourism industry in the Kashmir valley. The flow of both domestic and international tourists decreased day by day. As we mention in the above table that in past few years the growth rate seems to be negative, by which our tourism industry come under the trap of depression because every sector of Kashmir economy gets defang and many people lost their employment opportunity in this sector. Now people are changing their business trends because every year there is the political unrest happened in the valley which becomes common thing for we people. Recently in year 2016 there is a long spell of curfew of five months in summer season which is the main period of

tourism. So with this there is a huge loss of both lives and wealth.

Table 1.2: Effect of insurgency (2016) on tourism industry in valley

Consequence	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	41	82%
No	09	18%
Total	50	100%

Source: primary survey

Figure 1.2:

Source: primary survey

In table 1.2, 82 percent out of 50 respondents say that tourism gets affected due to insurgency and 18 Percent of the respondents say that tourism didn't get affected due to insurgency. Due to regular political unrest in valley tourism industry lost its prestige from last many years which is not a good sign for the future economic development of the Kashmir valley. It has been observed during survey that hotels, house boats and restaurants of Kashmir valley remain empty during the last year (2016) due to the landmark insurgency.

Conclusion: This study made it understandable that insurgency is a chief cause which affects the economy of Kashmir valley. Once the tourism is known as the backbone of Kashmir economy but now its contribution is decreasing day by day due to regular clashes and strikes, by which this sector contributes a little and people face unemployment especially the younger generation and by this they fall into the clichés of depression and do many unlawful activities. If the political unrest is not stopped the name

and fame of tourism of Kashmir valley once again become an undiscovered tourist place.

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